

Data Management Plan

V 1.0

Funaction

Aquatic fungal
biodiversity

FUNACTION — Aquatic FUNgal biodiversity: developing knowledge and strAtegies to inform ConservaTION priorities and measures

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1 FRAMEWORK & SCOPE

1.1 Administrative information

Project	FUNACTION: Developing knowledge and strategies to inform conservation priorities and measures
Responsible	FUNACTION Data and Digital Outputs Management Committee (DMC)
Deliverable	D4. Data Management Plan (DMP)
Work package	WP6 Management Coordination
Delivery date	29 June 2023
Availability	Public

Data Management Plan version history

Version	Date	Modification	Author(s)
0.0	29 June 2023	Original version	DMC
1.0	2 April 2024	Updated following Biodiversa+ review. Added APPENDIX 1 & APPENDIX 2. Formatted	DMC Led by J. Anderson

DMC - Data and Digital Outputs Management Committee

Country	DMC member	Active date (start)
Estonia	Veljo Kisand	April 2023
Germany	Alice Retter	April 2023
Italy	Emanuele Ferrari	April 2023
Portugal	Isabel Fernandes	April 2023
Sweden	Jennifer Anderson*	April 2023
Switzerland	Daniel Romero Mujalli	November 2023
USA	Cátia Canteiro	April 2023

*Committee Chair

Past members:

Andreas Bruder: April 2023 - November 2023

1.2 Scope

The DMP

- Supports common understanding and expectations among Partners and associated teams for the management of data associated with FUNACTION.
- Serves as a tool to ensure FUNACTION meets research community, partner institution, national and EU standards for data access (inclusive of FAIR principles and deposition of data into appropriate public repositories).
- Provides a mutually agreed framework defining the use, sharing, and storage of data.

1.3 Acronyms, abbreviations, & definitions

CA	Consortium Agreement
DMC	Data and Digital Outputs Management Committee
DMP	Data Management Plan
EDC	Engagement and Dissemination Committee
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
OC	Oversight Committee
Partner	Individual listed as main applicants in the funded project
PrID	Project unique identifiers that str traceable and stable IDs for samples, sample data, etc. They are persistent unique identifiers.
RP	Responsible Partner
SLU	Sveriges lantbruksuniversitet, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocols
ST	Sample type
Team	Participants in FUNACTION, often (but not exclusively) supervised by a Partner
USID	Unique Site ID is the base name for all samples collected at a specific site and sampling occasion
WP	Work Package. Numbers as per funded proposal

2 DMC

2.1 Authority for information

FUNACTION uses the management structure described in the funded project proposal and as outlined in the figure (right) wherein

“The Coordinator serves as the point of contact between Biodiversa+ and FUNACTION and has special oversight responsibilities, including chairing the OC and holding the tie breaking vote. The Deputy Coordinator supports the Coordinator in project leadership, and serves as acting-Coordinator if needed (e.g. acute illness). All Partners and their teams will cooperate towards the management of the project as follows:

Action 6.3 DMC: Management of data and digital outputs will be overseen by the DMC, ensuring application of FAIR principles, data security and availability, and adherence to the Data and Digital Outputs Management Plan (DMP) (D4).” FUNACTION application.

2.2 Membership, responsibilities, and scope

DMC will develop, implement, and update an operational FUNACTION Data and Digital Outputs Management Plan, support adherence to the DMP, and ensure the FUNACTION DMP meets research community, partner institution, national and EU standards.

- The DMC is composed of (minimum) one representative from each Partner institution. See page 1 for membership record.
- DMC meets twice per year (virtually), with interim virtual meetings and digital communications as needed.
- DMC representatives serve as the national responsible persons for data management.

3 DATA DESCRIPTIONS & EXPECTED DIGITAL OUTPUTS

3.1 Purpose of data collection

Data collection and research are in accordance with the FUNACTION Project Plan. The goals of the project are available online:

- Project webpage **FUNACTION.eu** (www.funaction.eu)
- **Biodiversa+**

3.2 Data types collected

Raw observational data

Primarily text and numerical. Text here refers largely to DNA sequence data and predefined metadata. Numerical data includes outputs of chemical analyses and environmental descriptors (e.g. temperature, pH, latitude, longitude). Images will be taken as part of the documentation of the sampling sites (metadata & communications materials), but are not planned for direct analysis.

Personal data

Names, and professional titles, phone numbers and email addresses of Stakeholders. See APPENDIX 1 for Information for Data Subjects, contact information, and storage details. These data are collected for the sole purpose of Stakeholder engagement and communication as defined in the project plan on the legal basis of Public Interest. Stakeholders may have the right to have their information erased, corrected or limited. Their rights can be exerted by contacting the authority indicated in APPENDIX 1. This list will not be shared or made public without the consent of the Stakeholders. This information will be stored in a secure non-cloud-based server with restricted access.

Personal data for FUNACTION Partners and Teams will be collected inclusive of name, affiliation, country, work email address, CV (e.g. of Partners as part of application process), photo (voluntary), social media handles (voluntary). This information is necessary for internal use to support communications and official reporting. Additional use of personal data is strictly with approval of the person(s) and may include acknowledgement of participation in the project on the website **FUNACTION.eu**, on X (or any other social media platforms), and in acknowledgement slides.

Photos

Photos collected within the project will be matched with the name of the photographer through the file naming convention, ensuring correct attribution for the photographer. By submitting photos to the project directories, it is understood by FUNACTION participants that their name WILL be public as the photo credit if/when their photos are used for FUNACTION presentations, publications, and communications to support correct and transparent attribution of credit.

Photos (continued)

In the case of photos that include people, they can only be submitted to the project if expressed permission from those pictured is provided. The initials of the person/people must be reported through the naming convention and their full name included in the file FUNACTION_photos_README. The photographer is responsible for ensuring that every pictured person understands that their photo and name (optional) WILL be public if/when the photos are used for FUNACTION presentations, publications, and communications.

DNA

DNA extracted from FUNACTION samples will be stored in Estonia and/or at the Partner institutions, as appropriate for the intended uses of the DNA. The location of the DNA sample will be recorded as within-FUNACTION metadata to keep track of the sample.

3.3 Expected data sizes

The amount of data generated depends in large part on which sequencing technologies are available at the time of sample submission. FUNACTION is prepared for the secure storage of 1-2 Tb of raw sequence data. This can be expanded with need. Personal data, sampling photos, and potentially films, are tentatively expected to require up to 100 Gb. FUNACTION has secure, GDPR compliant storage for these data. Estimation of expected data sizes is ongoing.

3.4 Expected datasets & outputs of long-term value

Description	WP	Public availability (upon publication when applicable)
18S- and ITS-rDNA metabarcode sequences	1, 2	UNITE, Mgnify (EMBL), GlobalFungi
Species/OTU distributions	1, 2	PlutoF, GBIF
Metagenomic sequences	2	Mgnify
Water physical-chemical datasets	1, 2	PlutoF
Ecosystem processes data	2	FUNACTION website, Zenodo
Scripts and workflows	1, 2, 3, 4	Zenodo, Github
Outreach, Reports, Policy briefs	3, 4, 5	FUNACTION website, Zenodo
Management documents	6	FUNACTION website, Zenodo
Scientific papers	1, 2, 3, 4	Published open access
Stakeholder personal information	4, 5	Not public, not shared

4 DATA COLLECTION

4.1 FUNACTION-generated primary data types and timing

Primary (raw) data generated by FUNACTION accumulated but not otherwise changed. The timing of data collection is estimated and subject to change.

- **18S- and ITS-rDNA metabarcode sequence:** Sequencing will be performed at SciLife Lab, Uppsala Sweden. The data will be generated in batches with the bulk of the data for WP1 and WP2 coming in autumn 2024. Note, some sequencing for WP1 predates the FUNACTION project and is currently stored in Estonia. The timing referred to in this section is for new data.
- **Metagenomic sequences:** WP2, expected winter 2024.
- **Water chemistry datasets:** Chemical analyses will be performed by Servicios de Seguridad Alimentaria y Desarrollo Sostenible del Centro de Apoyo Científico Tecnológico a la Investigación (C.A.C.T.I.) de la Universidad de Vigo (SSADS-CACTI), Spain. Data will be generated in batches with the bulk of the data for WP1 and WP2 coming by autumn 2024.
- **Site metadata:** Primarily collected in autumn 2023, and periodically updated with temporal sampling (WP2) and to complete sampling for WP1.
 - Data is collected using shared vocabulary and standardized reporting format through a “survey” form via **KoboToolBox** which compiles all responses for downloading.
 - Data identifiers are consistent with the survey data (see Data Identifiers section below).
 - The survey is viewable in **APPENDIX 2**.

4.2 Secondary data

Secondary (derivative) and Working datasets and storage fall under the responsibility of the RPs with guidance from the DMC. These datasets are typically derived from analysis pipelines and can be recreated by applying analysis/analyses, pipelines, or scripts. End products of these processes that are relied upon for reports/publications/etc... and scripts will be made public as per 3.4 (inclusive of details of their derivation).

4.3 Other data

- Primary data from FunAqua will be included in the project. FunAqua data were independently generated by the Estonian team before formation of FUNACTION. The producers of these data are within FUNACTION, but in the interest of maintaining proper credit, attribution, and use, we recognize this within the DMP.
- Other public datasets will be used in the course of analysis, e.g. environmental data, reference sequence data. Data use will be acknowledged and follow source-specific rules.
- Stakeholder information will be collected from FUNACTION participants (their individual networks), internet searches of publicly available information, and through a snowball approach where interested stakeholders are asked to suggest other relevant stakeholders. This process began during grant preparation and is expected to continue through project month 24.
- Photos will be taken as part of documentation of sampling sites and campaigns. These images are collected in a central directory on KoboToolbox and backed up to Google Drive together with appropriate metadata. Metadata is recorded in the file name according to the standards described within the DMP, with the addition of a unique code or name to identify the photographer (to support attribution of the image) and any people included in the photo.
- Internal Committee Archives will be maintained by each FUNACTION committee inclusive of decisions and documents of value. It is anticipated that these archives will be most useful during the project and within 1 year of the project end. The archives will be populated, maintained, and stored by a designated member of each committee such that they are accessible to the committee and full consortium. The archives must be backed up to a physical computer or server by that designated member regularly.

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5 DATA IDENTIFIERS

FUNACTION uses project unique identifiers (PrID) throughout, from sample collection to publication and associated datasets. All samples, datasets, sample submissions, raw data, photos, etc... must follow the agreed PID structure.

- The information in the site data collection survey (4.1) is used to produce the PrID.
- Sample type and replicate are specified on the sampling container and all derived data(sets).
- The PrID is flexible and can include additional information (e.g. data type or state) to accommodate identification of derivative data(sets).

5.1 Sample Naming Conventions (V1, Sept. 2023)

The Sample Naming Conventions are agreed by FUNACTION and also described in the FUNACTION Sampling Protocols.

Unique Site ID (USID):

The USID is the base name for all samples collected at a specific site and specific sampling occasion. See components Table 5.1 and abbreviations Tables 5.2 to 5.4.

FUNACTION: Refers to sampling of the targeted watersheds for WP2. Abbreviations chosen to reduce confusion with neighboring components of the USID and to NOT overlap with Country Codes.

FunAqua: Refers to sampling of the targeted watersheds for WP1.

USID	FUNACTION	= WC+SID+SO
	FunAqua	= CC+SID+SO

Name for a specific sample:

USID-ST

Table 5.1 Components of the USID and ST and their accepted values.

USID	Description
WC:	Watershed Code. See Table 5.3.
CC:	Country Code. See Table 5.4.
SID:	Site ID. number assigned to a specific site and <u>always re-used for that specific site</u> . If collecting in different teams, assign a different range of numbers for use by the different teams to avoid duplication. USE ## format for best machine readability. So for numbers 1-9, USE 01-09.
SO:	Sampling occasion. If a site is visited for the first time and/or the only time, it gets T1. Increase the # to denote the 2nd, 3rd etc. collection for temporal sampling.
ST:	Sample type

Table 5.2 Components of the USID and ST and their accepted values.

	Unique Site ID (USID)			Specific Sample types (ST)			
	Broad geographic ID	Site ID (SID)	Sampling occasion (SO)	Sterivex filter	Chemistry (water for chemical analysis)	Sediment	Litter
FUNACTION (WP2)	WC Table 5.3	## 01-30	T1-T8	W1, W2	C1, C2	S	L
FunAqua (WP1)	CC Table 5.4	## 01-30	T1-T8	W1	C1, C2	S	L

Table 5.3 Watersheds used as case studies and their codes.

Target Watershed	Watershed Code (WC)
Valgejõgi basin	VJ
Havel-Spree-Elbe basin	HE
Cávado River basin	CA
Douro River basin	DR
Luleålven	LU
Norrström	NR
Versilia	VA
Ticino-Po-IT	TP
Ticino-Po-CH	TS

Table 5.4 Country Codes for samples from WP1.

Country	Country Code (CC)	Country	Country Code (CC)
Albania	AL	Liechtenstein	LI
Andorra	AD	Lithuania	LT
Austria	AT	Luxembourg	LU
Belarus	BY	Malta	MT
Belgium	BE	Moldova	MD
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	Monaco	MC
Bulgaria	BG	Montenegro	ME
Croatia	HR	Netherlands	NL
Cyprus	CY	North Macedonia	NM
Czech Republic	CZ	Norway	NO
Denmark	DK	Poland	PL
Estonia	EE	Portugal	PT
Finland	FI	Romania	RO
France	FR	San Marino	SM
Germany	DE	Serbia	RS
Greece	GR	Slovakia	SK
Hungary	HU	Slovenia	SI
Iceland	IS	Spain	ES
Ireland	IE	Sweden	SE
Italy	IT	Switzerland	CH
Kosovo	KO	Ukraine	UA
Latvia	LV		

Example

LU09T1

WC: Luleälven = LU

USID: The number 09 was assigned to always refer to one specific site

SO: This is the first time or only time someone sample from this site = T1

LU09T1-W1

Refers to one of the Sterivex filters from the collection. NOTE–in the metadata, the amount of water filtered for each Sterivex will be individually reported.

Flexibility:

LU09T1-W1-MB1 = DNA sample relating to sample from above for barcode “1”

LU09T1-W1-MB1-raw = Raw sequence data from sample

LU09T1-1-wWWW-xy = USID + number to identify unique photo file + w[initials to identify people pictured in photo if applicable] + initials of photographer for photo credit

6 DATA SECURITY, STORAGE & COSTS

6.1 During the project period

- **Non-personal data backup at Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU):** Backup copies of non-personal data will be stored as follows to prevent data loss and data security. Secure data storage (managed by the university IT platform) with replication to offsite backup for the project period + 1 year. Direct access is limited to registered participants at SLU and data transferred to outside partners as needed using SFTP or via **restricted access** sharing via the FUNACTION Community on **Zenodo**.
 - Primary Sequence data
 - Site metadata and photos
 - Water chemistry data
- **Personal data:** Stakeholder personal data will be collected and stored using a secure SLU SharePoint with a physical server at SLU and restricted access.
- **Google drive:** FUNACTION has a shared directory on Google Drive. Use of this product shall be controlled through the sharing options on the site to be visible and editable only to/by those invited to participate in the directory and shall be limited as follows:
 - To include only non-sensitive and reproducible (or sufficiently backed-up) data. Personal data shall **NOT** be stored on Google Drive without the informed consent of the parties involved.
 - Primarily for purposes of active collaboration.
- **KoboToolBox:** During the period that samples are actively being collected for WP1 and WP2, sample metadata and photos will be stored using the KoboToolBox web collection system. These data are frequently backed up to a physical computer at SLU and separately to an additional server.
- **Partner institutions:** Partners, with the support of the DMC and DMP, are required to ensure the responsible backup of local and derived datasets that cannot be reasonably re-derived from scripts or pipelines through their Institutions and/or other reasonable and effective alternatives and following the principles herein (7.1). Reasonable and effective alternatives depend on data type and may include a **restricted access** Community at **Zenodo**, **GitHub**, etc. after approval from the DMC.

6.2 Long-term

Deposit of FUNACTION data in recognized public data repositories is a priority. Data and other digital outputs will be made available (see 3.4) following FAIR standards as per 7 DATA USE AND SHARING, herein.

Terms of use, data security, privacy, and other restrictions upon publication or official release of digital data and outputs follow the terms of use of the individual databases and are beyond the scope and control of FUNACTION. The databases are selected based on community standards, reliability, and limited restrictions.

FUNACTION partner institutions and funders have varying approaches/requirements for data archiving. Partners, with the support of their local member of the DMC, are responsible for meeting institutional and funder data storage and archiving responsibilities in addition to the terms herein.

6.3 Costs

Costs for the safe storage of primary data are assumed by Partner 1 (Coordinator) at SLU, other costs are assumed by the Partners. Budgeted costs cover secure storage of 2 TB with backup to a secondary site for 4 years (4000 SEK/TB/year). This extends 1 year past the project duration to ensure adequate opportunity for all data to be submitted to online repositories. Partners assume responsibility for their local costs of data backup, security and storage of primary data copies, secondary data and scripts.

6.4 Data Organization

Primary data: Directory structure and naming conventions will be established and updated by the DMC prioritizing FAIR principles and making use of public advice e.g. the following:

- **File Naming Conventions** from Longwood Research Data Management, Harvard.
- **File Naming** from ELIXIR-Belgium.

Directory and file names are expected to use the PrID when applicable (**5 DATA IDENTIFIERS**). Updating and version control of these datasets will be coordinated by the DMC.

Secondary data: These data are generated at Partner institutions and must adhere to Institutional requirements for Directory structure and naming conventions where applicable. To share these data among Partners (directly, via Zenodo Community or other) or with other approved recipients, the conventions for primary data must be applied.

7 DATA USE & SHARING

7.1 General principles

FUNACTION datasets will be formatted and made accessible at the time of publication or before (see **Criteria for external pre-publication sharing**) according to the community standards as follows:

FAIR: Described briefly here. Visit **GO FAIR** for details and advice.

Findable: at the appropriate time (below) data will be deposited in public data repositories with globally unique persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI) and linked to technical, sample and site-associated metadata. Where appropriate, sample metadata will be organized in CSV format, uploaded and managed by the community standard databases.

Accessible: Datasets will not require proprietary tools for access and access support is available through database/repository websites.

Interoperable: for the (meta)data, standardized formats and terminologies will be used to the extent possible and explanatory documentation provided in the linked readme.txt files.

Reusable: All samples will receive identifiers specifying the location, date and substrate, that will be used with all associated metadata and sequences ensuring traceability from field to database and interconnectivity among resulting datasets.

7.2 Within project data & digital output sharing

Primary data: Sequence data, physico-chemical data, land-use data, and other metadata will be produced through or by individual Partner institutions with direct registration (KoboToolbox, 4.1) to a shared site and/or prompt transfer of a digital copy of the raw data for backup at SLU. Copies of the raw data may also be made available within FUNACTION as described in **6.1 During the project period**.

The coordinator and DMC representative of Sweden has/have access to datasets at SLU and will provide data to Partners promptly upon request with the following exception.

In the unforeseen case that a request is made for data that is outside the scope of a Partner's project responsibilities (as defined by roles and expectations in the FUNACTION application), the request will be evaluated by the DMC prior to data availability. Access will be granted if all of the following are true:

1. Providing the data is consistent with and advances progress towards FUNACTION goals and objectives.
2. Access to the data does not infringe on other Partners rights and responsibilities within the project.
3. Co-authorships, collaborations, or other fair and transparent arrangements are formally (by email to DMC) and mutually pre-agreed.

Secondary data: These data are generated at partner institutions and are expected to be available among FUNACTION participants following the same principles and criteria as for Primary Data (above) but sharing is managed by the RP and/or RP designated responsible (e.g. national DMC representative). Sharing can be achieved by any secure method unless otherwise noted as excluded by the DMC and future versions of the DMP).

Outreach and engagement materials (digital): With the exception of sensitive information, these materials can and should be freely shared within FUNACTION. The EDC and DMC shall cooperate to ensure and encourage sharing and use of such materials.

7.3 Public access to data and digital outputs

Scientific papers: FUNACTION prioritizes publishing open access. Papers will be made publicly available from the time of publication. By mutual agreement among authors, the pre-publication version may be made publicly available via a field-appropriate and recognized pre-print archive.

Data that is the basis of Scientific papers: To support publication, datasets relied on for scientific papers will be deposited in public repositories (see **3.4 Expected datasets & outputs of long-term value**) following the guidelines herein (e.g. **7.1 General principles**) and made publicly available upon formal publication (does not include pre-review or pre-print versions).

The lead author and corresponding author of each manuscript is responsible for coordinating with the DMC and other work groups and authors to ensure that the data access is made public upon publication.

Outreach & engagement materials (digital): These outputs will be released to the public annually or earlier at the discretion of the DMC in cooperation with the EDC when they meet all criteria below.

Note: Publication to the **FUNACTION.eu** website and social media accounts can occur at any time—and is primarily at the discretion of the EDC but cannot conflict with restrictions within the DMP. Stakeholder names and contact information WILL NOT be shared (unless informed voluntary consent is documented) but stakeholders may be identified by organization name if necessary (as determined by the EDC).

1. Making the output public is consistent with and advances progress towards FUNACTION goals and objectives.
2. Access to output does not infringe on other Partners rights and responsibilities within the project.
3. Attributions are correctly and transparently acknowledged.
4. The materials have been verified to meet GDPR expectations.

7.4 Criteria for external pre-publication sharing

FUNACTION aims to produce the best possible scientific, societal, and policy outcomes. FUNACTION also has strong interests in capacity building and amplifying the impact of the project through building additional collaborations and supporting scientific and policy endeavors more broadly. To meet these ambitions, it can be in the best interests of FUNACTION to share data with non-FUNACTION participants before publication.

Partners shall request permissions for external pre-publication data sharing from the DMC in writing. Requests shall be evaluated within 14 days according to the criteria below. Partners shall be informed of such requests by their representative on the DMC and have the opportunity to express their views through their representative. Decisions by the DMC will be made in writing, inclusive of brief descriptions of how the three criteria are met or fail to be met by the request and any restrictions for use. The written decision shall become part of the DMCs archive.

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APPENDIX 1: DATA HANDLING DOCUMENTATION

Working draft

Information to data subjects about the processing of personal data in FUNACTION

Data controller

The Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU). The data protection officer at SLU can be reached at dataskydd@slu.se.

Others to be added upon completion of Joint Controllership Agreement or Joint Processor Agreement

Purpose

We are undertaking research supported by public funds. As part of the FUNACTION project, it is necessary to identify, communicate with, invite to stakeholder events, and/or seek feedback from parties (stakeholders) that might have interest in the work, be impacted by the work, and/or who can influence the work, as this is in the public interest.

Categories of personal data and sources

First name, last name, title and work or professional email address and phone number for representatives of governmental authorities, companies, non-profit organizations. First name, last name, and preferred email address for interested citizens who voluntarily provide this information and have requested communications on the project. Coordinates of sample sites are also collected.

Legal basis

Public Interest. This personal data processing is necessary in order to fulfill a task of Public Interest. This research has been funded by the EU as well as each individual partner state for the researchers involved.

The principle of public access to information

SLU and Partner Institutions that are public authorities, must apply the principle of public access to official documents. This means that all official documents, including personal data, that are not considered working material are public and can be released to anyone who requests them. However, if a document contains data that is subject to confidentiality, the document will not be released.

Storing data

Your personal data will be stored on a secure server at SLU. Data access is restricted to authorized individuals from the Partner Institutions. Your data will be stored until the latest 31 March 2027, one year past the project end point, to allow completion of project related tasks.

Your personal data will also be stored for as long as required by the Public Access to Information Act and the regulations on the archives of public authorities.

Your rights

You have the right, under certain circumstances, to have your personal data erased, corrected or limited. You also have the right of access to the personal data being processed, and you have the right to object to the processing of your data. To exert your rights, contact dataskydd@slu.se.

Comments: If you have any comments on the processing of personal data at SLU, contact dataskydd@slu.se.

If you are not happy with the answer provided by SLU, you can take your complaint to the Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection, imy@imy.se or +46 (0)8-657 61 00.

Read more about the Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection at <https://www.imy.se/other-lang/>

APPENDIX 2: METADATA SUBMISSION SURVEY

The survey is presented in a scroll format, where the user moves up and down the page. Here, the survey is divided into images (Figure A1–A5) in order of appearance. The survey is a dynamic interface, where options available change based on answers to 2 questions, Project, and Protection status. The alternative views are presented in Figure A6 and A7.

Figure A1

FUNACTION_v1

▼ Determine the Unique Site ID (USID) and declare the samples taken

***Project**

FUNACTION
 FunAqua

***Country**

***Watershed**

***Unique Site ID (USID)**
FUNACTION: WC=SID+SD; FunAqua: CC=SID+SD. WC & CC find from previous questions. SD = number assigned to a specific site and always re-used for that specific site. SD = Sampling occasion. If a site is visited for the first time and/or the only time, it gets '1'. Example: L0001.

***Sample types taken**
Select all that apply. NOTE: this will be used to trace samples—so double check you are accurate.

Sterivex (label as USID-W1)
 Sterivex (label as USID-W2)
 Water for chemical analysis (label as USID-C1) → DO NOT filter
 Water for chemical analysis (label as USID-C2) → filter this sample through 0.45 um
 Sediment (label as USID-S)
 Litter/Organic matter (label as USID-L)

Volume filtered for Sterivex filter (ml) -W1

Volume filtered for Sterivex filter (ml) -W2

Figure A2

▼ Describe the Site Generally

Is the sample taken from a protected area?
If No, which apply—add options? National Park, Nature Park (non-national park, e.g. regional), Natura 2000, Ramsar. Select all that apply.

Protected area
 Non-protected area

Dominant Land use/Ecosystem where you are
Question and categories should be evaluated for suitability before deploying the survey.

Grassland, meadow, similar
 Forest-natural (may be managed by not monocultures and straight rows etc...)
 Forest-tree farm (heavy management)
 Clear cut (not enough regrowth to call a forest)
 Agriculture-plant
 Agriculture-animal
 Urban-residential
 Urban/Industrial

Type of water body
When in the field, you would best describe the water body as? Note, you can give additional details in the comments.

Stream or river (lotic)
 Lake or pond (lentic)
 Reservoir (with human constructed dam)
 Estuarine (brackish)

Sediment type
Primary sediment type—if mixed, what is dominant? Gently move away organic matter to view. May be best to do downstream or AFTER taking water samples.

silt or mud
 sand
 gravel
 rock (typically larger than adult fist)

▼ Where and when are you?

Figure A3

▼ Where and when are you?

Capture your location
Capture your location with your device's GPS

latitude (x.y °)

longitude (x.y °)

altitude (m)

accuracy (m)

Search for place or address

Sampling Time

Sampling Date

▼ Water properties

Water Temperature (°C)

pH

Figure A4

pH

Electric Conductivity SPC (µS/cm)

Electric Conductivity C (µS/cm)

Oxygen saturation (%)

Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)

Turbidity
Record units next.

Turbidity Units

NTU
 FNU

▼ Photos and Notes

Photo 1
In 2 photos (Photo 1 and Photo 2) capture the upstream and downstream areas or to the right and left as you face standing water. DO NOT load panoramas.

[Click here to upload file. \(< 10MB\)](#)

Figure A5

▼ **Photos and Notes**

Photo 1
In 2 photos (Photo 1 and Photo 2) capture the upstream and downstream areas or to the right and left as you face standing water. **DO NOT** load panoramas.

↻

Photo 2
In 2 photos (Photo 1 and Photo 2) capture the upstream and downstream areas or to the right and left as you face standing water. **DO NOT** load panoramas. **DO NOT** load panoramas.

↻

Photo 3 – in front of you or other informative view

↻

Plant taxa from which leaves were collected in the Litter sample (if sampled at the site)
What types of leaves do you think you have collected? If you are able to ID them.

Additional field notes or comments

Figure A6

* **Project**

FUNACTION

FunAqua

* **Country**

Albania (AL)

Andorra (AD)

Austria (AT)

Belarus (BY)

Belgium (BE)

Bosnia and Herzegovina (BA)

Bulgaria (BG)

Croatia (HR)

Cyprus (CY)

Czech Republic (CZ)

Denmark (DK)

Estonia (EE)

Finland (FI)

France (FR)

Germany (DE)

Greece (GR)

Hungary (HU)

Iceland (IS)

Ireland (IE)

Italy (IT)

Kosovo (KO)

Latvia (LV)

Liechtenstein (LI)

Lithuania (LT)

Luxembourg (LU)

Malta (MT)

Moldova (MD)

Monaco (MC)

Montenegro (ME)

Netherlands (NL)

North Macedonia (NM)

Norway (NO)

Poland (PL)

Portugal (PT)

Romania (RO)

San Marino (SM)

Serbia (RS)

Slovakia (SK)

Slovenia (SI)

Spain (ES)

Sweden (SE)

Switzerland (CH)

Ukraine (UA)

Figure A7

▼ **Describe the Site Generally**

Is the sample taken from a protected area?
If PA, which apply—add options? National Park, Nature Park (non-national park, e.g. regional), Natura 2000, Ramsar. Select all that apply.

Protected area

Non-protected area

Dominant Land use/Ecosystem where you are
Question and categories should be evaluated for usefulness before deploying the survey.

Grassland, meadow, similar

Forest-natural (may be managed by not monocultures and straight rows etc...)

Forest-tree farm (heavy management)

Clear cut (not enough regrowth to call a forest)

Agriculture-plant

Agriculture-animal

Urban-residential

Urban/Industrial

Type(s) of protections
Select all that apply.

National Park

Other Park or general Reserve (e.g. regional)

Natura 2000

Ramsar

Type of water body
When in the field, you would best describe the water body as? Note, you can give additional details in the comments.

Stream or river (lotic)

Lake or pond (lentic)

Reservoir (with human constructed dam)

Estuarine (brackish)

Sediment type

Document credits & How to cite

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